

RUNNING HEAD: MS. WHEELCHAIR WISCONSIN

“I did not want to meet my Queen in a wheelchair”: The Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin dethroning
of 2005

Abstract

In 2005, the Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin pageant dethroned Janeal Lee after a picture in the paper showed her standing up. She requires a scooter, but can walk a few steps, and officials ruled that by appearing without her mobility aide, she forfeited the title. She argued that they defined disability narrowly. The board responded the pageant was for *wheelchair users*, not all disabled people. I analyze the controversy for identity development through argument.

The wheelchair draws messages as a flame draws moths. Stephen King identified a scene from the 1980 Canadian horror film *The Changeling*, featuring a haunted wheelchair which chased its victim through a house, as one of the scariest scenes in cinema history (1981). Iezzoni delves into the English common law governing mendicancy to discover that

A 1536 English statute forbade citizens from giving alms to beggars in the street, instead requiring them to donate to common, charitable funds controlled by local officials. As exceptions, citizens were allowed to offer alms directly to blind or “lame” persons. To this day, wheelchairs and white canes carried by blind persons remain the most potent, explicit symbols of disability (2000, p. 1160).

This potency may at times exist in an unchanneled, unrealized condition. Harrison and Kahn identify the wheelchair as a whitewash of other role messages, the identifying mark of “a perpetual state of ambiguity that was characterized by physical isolation and poor communication” (2004, p. 91). Tighe (2001) relates several narratives drawn from interviews with women who used wheelchairs for daily mobility; both ‘Loretta’ and ‘Sandra’ reported that people tended to see only the wheelchair and not the person. The wheelchair’s irresistible pull attracted attention away from all other identity features, but its detachability from their bodies created opportunities to write on the blank page left behind. ‘Loretta’ went on to explain that when she needed to discuss a problem with her apartment manager, she would take the extra time to *walk* to her apartment, because if she used the wheelchair, “She thought I was going to complain I guess. I came down to start a fuss that’s the attitude that she gave [sic]. And if I walked down and stood up, it was O.K.” (p. 516). Crossley (1999) told the story of James Brady’s appearance at the 1996 Democratic National Convention, and his few steps from his wheelchair to the podium. The audience roared its approval, perhaps not noticing that they had applauded him for *leaving* his wheelchair, validating his move *away* from the device that would

keep him mobile despite his permanent injury. Finally, Jerry Wolffe, a copy editor for the Oakland Press, reported that within the local community of people with disabilities, he encountered a definite hierarchy which elevated wheelchair users into a rarefied status of *truly* disabled:

At the time, I used canes to get around and felt I was not as well-accepted as those with more prominent disabilities, especially those using wheelchairs, even though I had been disabled since birth and had had 15 orthopedic surgeries. “Why aren't you using a wheelchair?” Marilyn Golden, a lawyer for the advocacy group, the Disability Rights Education and Defense Fund of Berkeley, Calif., asked me at the first training session. “I don't need one.” She turned her back to me and rolled away, obviously disgruntled. When I went back, six months later, to St. Louis to receive further training in the national civil rights law, I brought along a wheelchair because, by then, I could no longer walk. Others in the group hung out with me more, and I felt as though I were more accepted. “When Jerry first came to us, he was an outsider,” Golden said after I made a presentation on the rights of the disabled in regard to working. “But now, he is one of us.” (2005, ¶¶ 11-15)

One very public gathering of people in wheelchairs is the Ms. Wheelchair America pageant, an event established in 1972 by Philip Wood, a physician from Columbus, Ohio (Blundo, 2002), which ranks contestants on their accomplishments, knowledge of current events in the disability movement, and public speaking ability (Montgomery, 2002). Many of its participants report overcoming an initial ambivalence about being wheelchair users. Robin Ryerson, Ms. Wheelchair Colorado 1997, explains,

I went into a wheelchair kicking and screaming. My first one was heavy and I couldn't push it myself. One day I saw two women go by in sporty, cool-looking wheelchairs. I got one and it changed everything. It has opened so many doors and opportunities. I have

really blossomed because of my disability. It has made me stronger. It has made me who I am (Patty, 1997, p. 18A).

Lynn Naves, Ms. Wheelchair Florida for the same year, similarly reports that she clung to her walker until a friend showed her all the athletic and social opportunities that wheelchair use opened up; “life began when I started using a wheelchair,” she concludes (Schulte, 1997, p. 3).

One evening in 2004, a woman named Janeal Lee was shopping at Target for napkins, using her powered scooter for mobility as she did most days, when another woman named Gina Hackel introduced herself and suggested that Lee should enter the Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin pageant, a feeder event for the Ms Wheelchair USA competition (Vallis, 2005). Lee, whose reduced mobility is a consequence of muscular dystrophy, taught algebra at Kaukauna High School in Appleton, Wisconsin (Espino, 2005b). She entered the pageant, and on January 22, she was crowned Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin. A month and a day later, on February 23, her hometown newspaper, the Appleton Post-Crescent, ran a feature story on Lee’s win, accompanied by a picture of Lee standing up in her classroom (Espino, 2005d).

On April Fool’s Day 2005, the Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin board of directors made a decision that caught disability activists from coast to coast off-guard; it stripped Janeal Lee of the title of Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin, arguing that she had violated the contest rules by appearing in public while not seated in her wheelchair. Judy Hoit, board treasurer, provided the first published explanation of the decision: contestants must “mostly be seen in public using their wheel chairs or scooters. Otherwise, you’ve got women who are in their wheelchairs all the time and they get offended if they see someone standing up. We can’t have title holders out there walking when they’re seen in the public” (Espino, 2005b, ¶ 6).

Media attention lifted the controversy from local news, to national, to global. Lee spoke first with Appleton reporters, then on *Good Morning America*, the *Today* show, *Inside Edition*

and *A Current Affair*, and finally with journalists from Canada and the Netherlands (Espino, 2005d). Jay Leno joked about the decision on the *Tonight Show*, and Lee's students found over 4,000 hits for her name on Google (Espino, 2005e). Looking back, Lee said "I think I've raised more questions and comments and discussion than I could have in a year in the state of Wisconsin" (Vallis, 2005, ¶ 27). This paper will address only a few of the questions raised, as it analyzes the Lee controversy for insights into the management of the identities of women with disabilities through argumentation.

Review of literature

A number of feminist scholars have explored abrasions at the interface between gender and disability in identity scholarship (e.g. Silvers, 1998; Fox & Lipkin, 2002; Garland-Thomson, 2002). Much feminist work crafts sketches of feminine identity which end, as all sketchwork must do, at boundaries, and it is beyond those boundaries that women with atypical bodies or experiences are left searching for points of entry. Silvers locates this difficulty within cultural feminism, arguing that "Because women with disabilities have little access to the relationships and roles cultural feminism celebrates, they may be denied full womanly standing by feminist theories which do not appreciate a disability perspective" (p. 86). Treating this imperfection in the assemblage of feminist work as an opportunity, Garland-Thompson urges a turn toward disability in feminist writings not only to correct a deficiency, but also to nourish the project by enriching the growing understanding of how intersections between categories complicate the negotiation of identities: "[C]onsidering disability shifts the conceptual framework to strengthen our understanding of how these multiple systems intertwine, redefine, and mutually constitute one another . . . the cultural function of the disabled figure is to act as a synecdoche for all forms that culture deems non-normative" (p. 4). Because of its permeability, Garland-Thomson argues, the identity element of disability exceeds all other identities in making clear each

person's irreducibility:

Disability is an identity category that anyone can enter at any time, and we will all join it if we live long enough. As such, disability reveals the essential dynamism of identity.

Thus, disability attenuates the cherished cultural belief that the body is the unchanging anchor of identity. Moreover, it undermines our fantasies of stable, enduring identities in ways that may illuminate the fluidity of all identity (p. 20).

Alliance with disability scholarship may not be a straightforward project, however, given tension in the imperatives to re-appropriate identity while celebrating difference. The kernel of disability theory, through the past two decades, was assertion of the *social* model of disability as a departure from the *medical* model (Linton, 1998; Branfield, 1998; Branfield, 1999; Swain & French, 2000; Bagenstos, 2000; Tighe, 2001). Previously, disability had commonly been regarded as a personal tragedy, a medical condition handed over to management by doctors. The problem, Linton explained, was that "Society, in agreeing to assign medical meaning to disability, colludes to . . . keep it a personal matter and 'treat' the condition and the person rather than 'treating' the social processes and policies that constrict disabled people's lives" (p. 11). Activists insisted that it was societal configuration that stripped them of power and mobility, not their bodies; doorways that would not admit wheelchairs were the obstacles, not their neuromuscular injuries. The onus for inclusion fell upon those who made choices in structuring public space, not on the disabled individuals. The Americans with Disabilities Act set in motion material changes, actual architectural changes, that fulfilled this reallocation of responsibility. As Bagenstos explained,

. . . the disability rights argument is not that disability is entirely a social creation, only that it must be understood as the result of an interaction between biological restrictions and the broader physical and social environment - and that the greater part of the

disadvantage attached to "disability" is best addressed through attempts to change the environment. (pp. 430-431)

Turbulence *within* the disability movement emanated from the necessary enabling moves that made these gains possible. Linton, speaking of the assignment of group identity to disabled people, concluded that "These designations, as reclaimed by the community, are used to identify us as a constituency, to serve our needs for unity and identity, and to function as a basis for political activism" (p. 12). However, Crossley warns that "disabled people are an extremely heterogeneous bunch. . . . Due to this heterogeneity, disability theorists are particularly sensitive to their inability to speak to the experience of all disabled people" (1999, p. 664). Silvers argues this is especially true for disabled women:

Homogenizing people who function differently from one another injures some, even if advancing others. Collectivizing disability perspectives thus competes with acknowledging the singular ways in which people with disabilities succeed. Consequently, being identified with a disability group norm appears to be no more advantageous to the equal recognition of all women with disabilities than is their being held to a gendered norm (p. 104).

And Davis (2002), fitting disability activism into a historic trajectory followed by other civil rights movements such as African-Americans and homosexuals, suggests that people with disabilities may be moving into a second, more complex, phase of identity growth:

The first phase . . . implies a pulling together of forces, an agreement to agree for political ends and group solidarity, along with the tacit approval of an agenda for the establishment of basic rights and prohibitions against various kinds of discrimination and ostracism. In a second wave, a newer generation of people within the identity group, ones who have grown up with the liberatory models well in place, begin to redefine the struggle and the

subject of study. They no longer seek group solidarity since they have a firm sense of identity. In a second wave, the principals are comfortable about self-examining, finding diversity within the group, and struggling to redefine the identity in somewhat more nuanced and complex ways. Often this phase will produce conflict within a group rather than unity (pp. 10-11).

Piastro (1993) identified, at an early stage, the branching of activist paths for people with disabilities: “The disability cultural movement . . . is about individuals’ stories celebrating who we are, learning who we have been. And woven through them all is a common thread of survival, restricted choices, enforced poverty, and benign oppression” (p. 9E). Instead of marshalling power by concentrating it, by emphasizing teamwork and unity, people with disabilities now were encouraged to describe and celebrate their *differences*, even as they found threads of similarity in the *quality* of experience that helped all feel stronger and more connected to one another. This move complicated relations with non-disabled people, as Swain and French noted that “many non-disabled people readily accept the social model, albeit superficially and at a basic conceptual level. . . . [but] Non-disabled people are much more threatened and challenged by the notion that a wheelchair-user could be pleased and proud to be the person he or she is” (p. 570).

This move to incorporate difference is especially critical if disability activism is to ally itself with feminist work, because being female *and* disabled creates, as with other intersections, a synergy of complications that is greater than the sum of its parts. Nosek & Hughes (2003) note that the overwhelming majority of medical research into therapy and treatment for physical impairment happens during post-war periods when veterans, almost all male, come home from the front. Thus, little of it accounts for the different roles and different bodies women inhabit. Women with disabilities are more likely to suffer physical abuse, as abusers are able to withhold assistance as a form of abuse, and resources for escaping abuse are less accessible to disabled

women than women without physical impairment (Nosek et al., 2001). McLaughlin (1990) points out that most women's clothes are not designed to fit properly when one is seated, and most easy-access clothes worn by women who need assistance at life tasks are extremely drab. Silvers summarizes a number of population-based measures of well-being and life satisfaction:

[W]hile more than half of non-disabled men, non-disabled women, and disabled men are employed, less than half of women with disabilities have employment. They are the group most likely to remain unmarried. Among persons who have married and are not widowed, 25% of female disabled, while only 12% of male non-disabled, 15% of female non-disabled, and 11% of male disabled, are divorced or separated (1998, p. 89).

Janeal Lee's moment of championship provides an opportunity to examine a very well publicized, and very thoroughly discussed, problematization of identity at this particular intersection. Lee's identity as a woman with a disability was evaluated and rejected by guardians of the orthodoxy. The mutually-correcting messages generated in the controversy that followed flesh out the speculative inquiry of disability researchers, providing an opportunity to watch the clash of perspectives grounded in a particular issue. The identity traces are there to be found in the arguments.

Hazen and Williams (1997), directing attention to the "'constitutive turn' in argumentation theory," report an intensifying "concern with argument as an integral dimension of all communication which has to do with coming to be as well as coming to know or, in the more pragmatic realm, simply convincing to do" (p. v). Much of the work describing argument's interplay with identity concerns itself either with ethnic or national identities (Lake, 1997; Ishiyama et al., 1997), or *professional* identities, such as that of the physician (Srader, 2005; Srader, 2006). Bruner urges a turn to identity management in feminist argument study, conceding that "Yes, we must identify, but we also must ensure that enabling constraints are constantly

available for critical inspection. And this is what I suggest should be the guiding ethic for feminist argumentation” (1996, ¶ 36).

In the sections that follow, I will examine the controversy over Janeal Lee’s dethroning from the Ms Wheelchair Wisconsin 2005 title. I will first provide additional background about the pageant itself to highlight its unsettled organizational identity, and then examine the arguments deployed by Lee and the pageant organizers. The final sections will discuss the arguments, draw conclusions, and suggestion directions for future research.

Positioning the pageant

Organizers of the various Ms. Wheelchair pageants have long insisted that it was *not* a beauty pageant. Nelda Kampff, Ms. Wheelchair Florida 1996, remarked, “This is by no means, in any form, a beauty pageant. We like to refer to it as an achievement competition” (Thompson, 1996, p. 1). Barbara Kramer, pageant director for the 1997 national contest, concurred: “This is not a beauty pageant. This is a competition of achievement” (Jefferson, 1997, p. B2). Gina Hackel reported that in the Wheelchair Wisconsin pageant, beauty played “zero” role (Hartzell, 2005b, ¶ 7). And yet, however vehemently they distanced themselves from the beauty contest image of the more well-known Miss America pageant, at times their words and practices betrayed them. Often they offered the denial in the same breath as praise for their winner’s physical appearance: “Beauty is not a criterion, even though Melissa looks like she fell out of a magazine,” said Stacey Hubbard, 2003 pageant coordinator for Ohio (Ellis, 2003, p. 1B). Kramer, disputing Hackel’s calculation, asserts that “Only about 20 percent is based on poise and personal appearance” (Patty, 1997, p. 18A). And since nominees for the Nobel or Pulitzer prizes are not expected to wear “sequins, ball gowns and high heels” (Luzadder, 1997, p. 42A), and the winners are not adorned with tiaras and sashes (Norton, 2000), the insistence that the pageant only awards achievement rung hollow. When Janeal Lee was stripped of the Wisconsin title, her

preparations for the national pageant were well underway; she “had carefully selected two dresses and matching shoes that would not clash with her teal-green motorized scooter. Janeal Lee also had started growing her hair long, [and] scheduled an appointment for professional photos” (McCormick, 2005, ¶¶ 1-2).

Even before the Lee controversy propelled the pageant into national headlines, different participants aligned its purpose with the opposing ends of the social/cultural dialectic. Several winners, both state and national, said it gave them credibility and visibility, a platform from which they could reach non-disabled audiences and share their own experiences. Ruthee Goldkorn, Ms. Wheelchair California 2001, commented, “Now people pay attention. Having the title has given me validity” (Salisbury, 2001, p. E2). Ileana Cruz, Ms. Wheelchair Florida 1996, spoke of wanting to reach women caught in a tricorn intersection of categories: “Hispanics tend to be more protective. I want to show them that a woman in a wheelchair can be independent, that she can achieve Right now, people with disabilities have more rights than ever to access. The biggest barrier now is attitudinal. I’d like to dispel some of those myths” (Thompson, 1996, p. 1). Even Cinda Hughes, Ms. Wheelchair America 2003, who publicly called on the entire board to resign for their mishandling of Lee’s dethroning, nevertheless praised the pageant itself, saying “I love to see the respectful admiring looks of the children I meet. I love to see how perceptions change right before my eyes. The work is so valuable” (Lewin, 2005, ¶ 16). The explicit goal of the pageant’s organizers was to elevate a spokesperson to notoriety: Barbara Cramer, in the same statement in which she assessed appearance as 20% of the scoring criteria, described the event as “the 25th Ms. Wheelchair America Program . . . We call it a program because it’s not a pageant. We are looking for an articulate spokesperson, someone accomplished who can go around America with the message that it’s OK to be disabled” (Patty, 1997, p. 18A).

Other participants resisted the pageant’s positioning as a push for social change, locating

the event instead within a cultural or celebratory perspective on disability. Kris Ann Piazza, Ms. Wheelchair New York 2000, complained about being labeled a spokesperson, saying “I am not going to say I am a representative of all of the disabled community. I am not their voice. I am representative of one individual” (Norton, 2000, p. 1C). Nelda Helmbrecht, one of the board of directors for Ms. Wheelchair Florida, pinpointed the “most outstanding” aspect of the event as the way “the girls hold on together. The camaraderie is just incredible by the night of the competition ... you are not even disappointed (if you aren’t chosen) because one of your friends will have been chosen” (Clary, 1991, p. 1). Carl Beck, coordinator of judges for the pageant, moved the function beyond friendship and enjoyment to more transformational forms of support: “It’s a good program. It is as much an education group as a self-help group. We see these young women come together and educate each other” (Clary, 1991, p. 1). Janeal Lee said of her reason for participating, “I was most looking forward to competing in the pageant so that I--I would have a chance to network with other disabled women in my state, and I was very excited when I won” (Curry, 2005, ¶ 5).

Quite apart from the contestants’ struggles, the pageant itself suffered from an unstable identity: was it pure recognition of achievement, or a more traditional beauty pageant? If only one, why include elements of the other? Was it a headhunt for the perfect spokesperson, or a gathering of marginalized people to pool their strength and celebrate their triumphs? Upon this cracked foundation of organizational mission, the exchange of arguments over Lee’s dethroning unfolded.

The controversy

Lee’s initial response to the board’s reasoning was straightforward: pageant officials had been given full notice of her ability to walk before they awarded her the title. She reported in several interviews that she had notified Gina Hackel that she walked in her classroom (Espino,

2005b; Nunnally, 2005). She told Ann Curry of the *Today Show*, “I did inform the pageant official that I could stand and walk in my classroom prior to entering the pageant, so the coordinator in Wisconsin was aware of my abilities before I ever entered the pageant” (Curry, 2005, ¶ 9). Catherine Gugala, one of the contest judges, came forward to report that she had seen Lee stand and walk on the day of the pageant, insisting that “I knew she could walk, but I also knew her main mobility was her scooter. I would be very surprised if someone in the Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin pageant didn’t know” (Espino, 2005d, ¶¶ 22-23). And when Lee did walk, the movement was sudden and sporadic, stiff-jointed, and she had to brace herself against furniture for each step (McCormick, 2005). Lee conceded that Hackel had expressed concern when the *Post-Crescent* story and picture first ran in February, but said Hackel had told her the national office had okayed it, since the story reported her disability (Nichols, 2005).

Pat O’Bryant, executive director of the pageant, began the organization’s defense by pointing out that there was a constant problem with coordinators not understanding the rules, and noting that each year she had worked with the pageant, there were several disqualifications (Espino, 2005c). She then cited language in the contract Lee signed upon winning the Wisconsin title, which spelled out: “I understand that no time while I am appearing as Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin will I appear not in my wheelchair” (Lowe & Espino, 2005, ¶ 15), and concluded, “The young lady who was chosen did not meet the requirements to compete as Ms. Wheelchair America” (McCormick, 2005, ¶ 7). Gina Hackel concurred: “All I can say is she does not meet the physical requirements. It stated it in her contract -- She should’ve known about it” (Espino, 2005b, ¶ 12), and a statement released by the Ms. Wheelchair America organization read, in part,

For better or worse, the founders of this pageant included a rule, which is stated in the national and Wisconsin guidelines, that the winner must appear in her wheelchair or scooter when in public. While we feel for Ms. Lee, and understand the concern that many

have shared with us, a rule is a rule in any contest (Ms. Wheelchair America, 2005, ¶ 4).

From these two simple, blunt appeals to black-and-white judgments, the two sides' arguments grew into more nuanced positionings within the dialectic of social versus cultural emphasis in disability activism. Lee spoke against the organization's rule, arguing that it drew arbitrary and unproductive boundaries around the concept of "disability," and excluded people who needed support and advocacy:

The way they see it, you're either 100 percent disabled or 0 percent disabled, when in reality everyone is somewhere in between. It gives us a narrow view of who a person with a disability is. I've been made to feel as if I can't represent the disabled citizens of Wisconsin because I'm not disabled enough (Espino, 2005b, ¶¶ 7-8).

She furthermore disputed the contest's claim to appropriate her identity at *all* times, including during her working hours, pointing out that "the rule states that while you're--you're appearing as Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin. I was not appearing as Ms. Wheelchair Wisconsin. I was being Mrs. Lee in my classroom" (Curry, 2005, ¶ 9).

From criticizing the contest organizers' stance, Lee asserted her own determination to keep her identity authentic, to refuse to groom herself to meet the pageant's image:

I am not going to compromise who I am as a person to fit the stereotype, to have a title. That's not what I'm about. I'm not going to pretend to be more disabled so I can fit the mold. I'm not going to give up mobility now for a certain "look," because there will be a day when I can't walk at all, when I can't stand. That day's in the future for me. I don't know when (Nunnally, 2005, p. B1).

She concluded, "I wouldn't have been out of place even if I had been the only one there who could walk. I am disabled. That's the bottom line." (Espino, 2005d, ¶¶ 36-37)

Pageant officials and participants responded, defending their focused requirements as

necessary to pursue their mission. O'Bryant told a reporter that although everyone was welcome to participate in the pageant, those who didn't meet the requirements to be a contestant could only support it by helping in an organizational role (Espino, 2005c). Hackel commented, "The eligibility criteria is [sic] very specific, just like Special Olympics. Kids who don't have cognitive disabilities are not eligible for Special Olympics and nobody has a problem with that" (Imrie, 2005, ¶ 9). And Kim Jerman, the second runner up who ultimately *did* accept the title, argued against allowing people who were not *dependent* on their wheelchair to compete: "It is not fair for me who needs a wheelchair all day. It is named Ms. Wisconsin Wheelchair for a reason. It is not named Ms. Disability" (Imrie, 2005, ¶ 13). Even Lee occasionally stumbled into an essentializing line of argument, arguing at one point, "It's not as though I had a knee injury or had a surgery of some kind that I'm going to recover from. I was born with a progressive disease, If that doesn't qualify someone as a disabled person, I'm not really sure what does" (Vallis, 2005, ¶ 12), a formulation of the identity which might exclude those forms of physical impairment that could respond to experimental treatment, including blindness, deafness, and many types of paralysis.

Discussion

A number of African-American studies scholars have explored the gradations of lightness and darkness within that racial community. Hunter (1998) documents the move to embrace darkness during the civil rights era, the "black is beautiful" changes in fashion and grooming that "radically altered, even if temporarily, the orientation of beauty for African Americans" (p. 523). Cruz-Jansen (1999) notes that dark-skinned members of a race may resent those who identify as the same race, but have lighter skin, and Baynes (1997) recounts experiences of defending light-skinned African-Americans against criticism that they aren't *really* on board, that their sympathies lie more with whites. Baynes cites both historical and contemporary evidence to

suggest that color preference is retreating from *both* extremes, that brown people are coming to be regarded as more attractive than those who are extremely dark or extremely light.

Janeal Lee was able to walk only when surrounded by furniture, only for short distances, and only on particular days when her illness wasn't flaring up. Yet even with all those limitations, she was able to rise from her scooter and walk, which placed her in the position of the light-skinned African-American, who bears a physical trace of the oppressor, and thus may not be fully accepted as an authentic member of the community drawn together by marginalization. Much is written in disability studies about people who don't *feel* disabled, and thus try to "pass" as members of the non-disabled world, just as some light-skinned African-Americans have set out to "pass" as Caucasians; however, few authors or activists devote attention to the converse problem, the drawing of boundaries too tightly, so that they shut out those who clearly *have* experienced exclusion, but aren't accepted by others who have experienced similar treatment.

Lee, in her arguments against the pageant board's decision, positioned herself as a disability activist in the cultural camp. She celebrated her own experience, refusing to accept a uniform identity and criticizing the event's organizers for enforcing a somatic orthodoxy that excluded people whose bodies, although impaired, did not exhaust the checklist of attributes they had created to protect the image they believed would best advance their goals. She pursued *inclusion* and *support*, rather than doing what was necessary to ascend to a position of *leadership*. Borrowing Foss and Griffin's (1995) concepts, she conceptualized the various Ms Wheelchair crowns as sites of *invitation*, rather than hierarchical pedestals for persuasion. While, ultimately, she and other disability activists adopted a more aggressive tone, moving in their duel of statements and interviews far beyond the sharing of perspectives Foss and Griffin prescribe, they all nevertheless spoke approvingly of the breaking of invisibility and the elevated public

profile of the issue, suggesting that perhaps at some level they could view themselves, in retrospect, as collaborators in educating others by performing a controversy before cameras. Lee told Ann Curry,

I think the best thing that has come out of all of this is that it has made national news and even international news. People are discussing this very important issue of disability awareness. And that's the reason I got involved in the pageant in the first place.

Unfortunately, I'm not able to continue with the pageant or compete at the national level.

However, I have gotten a message out there that disability awareness is very critical.

(Curry, 2005, ¶ 15)

Both sides in the controversy exercised their own will, adopted and defended their own judgments, which signaled an encouraging stride forward from previous eras in the history of disability activism, when activists struggled mightily to escape from having others' will imposed on their everyday life tasks and medical decisions. Both sides spoke to an enormous, nationwide and worldwide audience, and both began from the assumption that disability is not a tragedy, not a source of shame. The controversy signaled progress, and churned up latent tension in the movement, preparing the way for future progress by making others aware of, and involved in, the dispute. Pageant organizers saw image management as a powerful tool that they wished to apply to social barriers to disability accommodation, so they made a move of internal exclusion within the community to filter candidates for their representative down to the ideal. Lee and her supporters questioned that move, suggesting that propriety was not the right criterion for inclusion in a group of people constituted by a history of exclusion. Whatever the outcome of the dispute, its enactment dislodged an untenable status quo of identity stalemate, and forced activists to address the dilemma between idealized image and the reality that impairments are diverse and do not tumble neatly into taxonomies. Even if the resolution of the dispute would

never be called Solomonic/Athenic, no one could take refuge in ignorance of the difficulties of breaking women's experience of disability into public awareness.

Conclusion

Janeal Lee was not left to brood over her lost glory for very long. On April 26, 2005, the World Association of Persons with Disabilities (WAPD) named her Miss disABILITY International, a brand new title created in response to the Ms Wheelchair America decision. Lee said of her new title, "There were no parameters for how disabled you are or what disability you do have, so I qualify! It's not like I'm being told, hey you won the title and then two months down the road, oh guess what, you're not disabled enough for us" (Espino, 2005f, ¶ 14). Notably, the new title did *not* include a tiara (Appleton teacher given, 2005). Great American Financial, an Ohio insurance firm, gave Lee all the prizes she had been forced to return when stripped of her title, including a new scooter and an overnight stay at an accessible resort (Nufer, 2005).

Hackel and other pageant organizers weathered a conflict of interest scandal involving the law firm that both represented the pageant organization *and* filed ADA lawsuits against businesses across Wisconsin and in other states. The lawsuits were settled, and the law firm withdrew from involvement with the pageant (Lowe & Espino, 2005; Lowe, 2005). Barbara Cramer renewed her push to drop the word "pageant" from the event, commenting, "We're not stressing the disability, we're stressing the person. . . . Those of us really involved in athletics would say, 'Oh my God. Why would we want to be involved in a pageant?' The (participants) want to be known for sports activity" (Espino, 2005g, ¶¶ 33, 38).

The wheelchair continues to be a powerful magnet for people's attention and the condensation of messages. Lee uses it each day in her classroom; as a teaching tool, it rivals her chalkboard:

Familiarity leads itself to acceptance. This isn't just about me. I really see myself as a

representative to the disabled in the community. Sometimes they'll ask me if it (scooter) needs snow tires. Does it run on gas. Why do I use it if I can walk. I'm very open about it (her disability). That's critical. That's the educational part (Espino, 2005a, ¶¶ 9-13).

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